

ReliefF-based feature ranking and feature selection for monitoring induction motors

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Abstract— A feature is a measured property of a monitored system. Feature extraction in condition monitoring requires domain knowledge about a system and its possible fault cases. To find the most sensitive features for fault patterns, one has to evaluate the relevancy of features. In this paper the authors use ReliefF, which is a K-nearest neighbors-based feature selection algorithm, to evaluate the features extracted from an induction motor dataset. The dataset contains data from eight different health states of an induction motor. Feature relevancy is calculated for each health state. The selected features are fed into a simple Bayesian binary classifier to calculate the most likely health state. The method provides insight into the relevance of features by sensor type and also by signal processing type. The evaluation of similarity among the selected features can help identify similar faults. The results obtained emphasize the importance of domain knowledge in the proper design of features. Furthermore, by considering experimental data obtained for multiple loading and noise conditions, the feature selection method indicates features which are best suited for diagnosing specific faults, regardless of external conditions. Such information can support the creation of robust monitoring systems.

Keywords—Feature selection; Relief; Bayesian classifier; Induction motors; Diagnostics; Condition monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

The condition monitoring of induction motors is a well-established field, which is due in part to their prevalence in industrial applications. Fault diagnosis is achieved by collecting sensor data over a period of time and then analyzing the data via data-driven or model-based methods. Signal processing methods are applied to the raw data to extract only the valuable and representative information. This step is called feature extraction, where feature is defined as a measured property of the monitored object [1]. Feature extraction in condition monitoring requires domain knowledge about the equipment or system and its possible fault modes. However, even with the use of domain knowledge one might end up with many redundant, noisy or irrelevant features. The task of feature selection is to reduce the number of features to a

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smaller subset, where the features are less prone to noise, less correlated and only the most relevant features are kept for the design of condition monitoring systems [2].

Feature selection can reduce complexity and computation time by allowing simpler models to be used, build understandings of the data, the features and the faults in depth and also contribute to the improvement of the prediction performance of a diagnostics methods [1]. In the case of installing and evaluating sensors for condition monitoring, feature selection can be used to assess if sensor features are relevant or necessary. Sensors which do not provide any added value on the feature level to the monitoring task may subsequently be eliminated, potentially reducing the cost of the monitoring system.

In this paper the authors introduce a new application of ReliefF, which is a K-nearest neighbors-based feature selection algorithm, in the evaluation of features extracted from an induction motor dataset. The dataset contains data from eight different health states of an induction motor; in addition to data recorded from a healthy motor, data is also acquired from motors with rotor faults, stator faults and bearing faults. The selected features are fed into eight Bayesian binary classifiers in order to calculate whether the observation belongs to a certain fault class or not. As the feature selection is conducted for each fault class, the feature relevancy differs from class to class. Based on the selected features for each fault class, one can observe which signal processing techniques and sensors are the most relevant to the monitoring of a certain fault class. The evaluation of similarity among the selected features can help in identifying similar faults. The described feature selection method is able to identify those features that are less sensitive to noise and less dependent on loading conditions. Such information can support the creation of robust monitoring systems.

The paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 the ReliefF-based feature selection algorithm and a Bayesian binary classifier for fault detection are introduced. Section 3 describes the induction motor dataset, which was used for the validating the methods. The results are presented in Section 4, which are

discussed further in Section 5. Finally in Section 6 conclusions are drawn, pointing out the advantages, limitations and possible use cases of the method.

II. METHODS

A. ReliefF

The original Relief algorithm [3] is a supervised feature selection method which works for classification problems with two classes. It randomly takes an observation and searches for its nearest neighbor in the same class (nearest hit) and in another class (nearest miss). For each feature the algorithm calculates a relevancy index, giving positive weights to those features which are close to each other in the same class and giving negative weights to those features, which are close to each other in the other class. In this way, those features which result in the best class separation throughout the observations in the training set will be assigned a high relevancy index.

Relief is a multivariate filter providing a complete order of features based on the relevance index; in other words it is able to rank individual features according to their relevance in the context of other features [4]. ReliefF extends Relief to multi-class problems [5]. The authors chose ReliefF for a two-class classification problem, as it is more robust against incomplete and noisy data taking not only the nearest, but the k-nearest neighbors [6]. Fig. 1 provides an algorithmic description of ReliefF in case of two class labels.

ReliefF algorithm

Input: All features and class labels for each observation in the training set

Output: A relevancy index vector W , which contains the calculated relevancy of each feature

1. set all weights $W[A] := 0$
2. **for** $i=1:m$
3. randomly select an observation O_i
4. find k nearest hits H_j and k nearest misses M_j
5. **for** $A:=1:a$
6. $W[A] := W[A] - \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{\text{diff}(A, R_i, H_j)}{m \cdot k} + \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{\text{diff}(A, R_i, M_j)}{m \cdot k}$
7. **end**
8. **end**

Fig. 1. The ReliefF algorithm for classification problems with two classes [5]

The $\text{diff}(A, O_1, O_2)$ function for numeric features calculates the Manhattan distance between the values of the features A for two observations O_1 and O_2 (Eq. 1). It is also used to calculate the distances between observations in order to find nearest neighbors.

$$\text{diff}(A, O_1, O_2) = \frac{I_1(A) - I_2(A)}{\max(A) - \min(A)} \quad (1)$$

B. Bayesian classification

A Naïve Bayes classifier [7] was chosen to classify the observations into F_N fault categories. From the healthy training data feature distributions are calculated for each feature using Kernel Density Estimation (KDE). Thresholds are set

symmetrically on the lower and upper end at 2.5% and 97.5% of the cumulative density functions. For any given observation, the probability that it belongs to fault category F_i given that a feature y_k crossed its associated threshold is calculated in the following way according to Eq. 2.

$$P(F_i | y_k) = \frac{P(y_k | F_i) \cdot P(F_i)}{P(y_k)} \quad (2)$$

Where $P(y_k | F_i)$ contains the likelihood of feature y_k crossing its threshold, given it belongs to F_i . $P(F_i)$ is the prior probability and $P(y_k)$ is the probability of a feature crossing its threshold in the whole dataset. The probability that an observation is classified as fault F_i is calculated in the same manner taking into account all of the features. The final prediction of the classifier will be the fault class which has the highest posterior probability (index of the Maximum a posteriori class).

C. Binary classifiers for fault diagnostics

Even in the case that there are more than two fault classes, there is an advantage associated with using binary classifiers: there is no need to use the same feature set for diagnosing the different fault classes. In the case of N faults, the fault patterns and the most relevant features can significantly vary amongst the different faults. Feature selection is conducted for each fault class, finding those features which provide the best class separation from the rest of the observations ('others'), obtaining an optimized feature set. The structure of the N binary classifiers is shown below in Fig. 2 for diagnosing N fault categories.

Fig. 2. Structure of the Bayesian binary classifier

Feature selection is applied for each fault class against the ('others') using the training set. Based on the relevancy index, the first z features are selected to be subsequently used as inputs to the Bayesian classifiers. Each classifier calculates the probability of a set of features belonging to a particular fault class, then the results of the N classifiers are fused on the decision-level:

1. If only one classifier, other than 'others', is predicted then that prediction is considered final
2. If two or more classifiers predicted other than 'others' then:

- if there is highest probability, it is the final prediction
 - if the top highest probabilities are equal – the observation is classified as ‘not known’
3. If no classifier predicted other than ‘others – the observation is classified as ‘not known’

III. DATASET

An induction motor dataset was used for validating the described methods. Healthy and faulty data was collected under different loading and environmental conditions from four SZJKe 14a induction motors, which had the same working parameters: a nominal active power of 0.8 kW and a nominal rotor speed of 1400 rpm. An eddy current brake connected to each motor provided load. For a detailed description about the experimental set-up, readers are directed to [8]. Eight different health conditions were collected during the experiments, for each fault case 3-5 different loading conditions were tested.

- F0: Healthy motor
- F1: Stator fault: Phase one bypassed in the first phase
- F2: Stator fault: Phase one bypassed in half of the first phase
- F3: Stator fault: Phase-phase short-circuit
- F4: Stator fault: Phase-phase short-circuit with offset point
- F5: Stator fault: Break of half of the phase one
- F6: Rotor fault: Two broken rotor bars
- F7: Bearing fault: Outer raceway defect

5 different sensor types were used: 4 Microflown signals (measuring particle velocity), 3 microphone signals (measuring sound pressure), 2 current signals, 4 vibration signals and 3 voltage signals provided 16 signals during the experiments. The data collection sampling rate was 51.2 kHz, each test lasted for 30 seconds. For each loading condition measurements were taken with and without background noise, which provided a total number of 58 datasets.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

A. Design of features

The 30-second datasets were split into 0.5-second windows, forming 60 observations per dataset, in total 3480 observations for the 58 datasets. For each observation the following time domain features were extracted: Root Mean Square (RMS), Skewness, Kurtosis, Maximum Peak, Peak-to-Peak, and Crest Factor (CF). For each observation the following frequency domain features were extracted (both from the amplitude spectrum (SA) and from the envelope spectrum): Spectrum Area, Frequency Center (FC), the amplitude of the components at the first two harmonics of the supply frequency (50, 100 Hz), the first three harmonics of the rotation speed (1X, 2X, 3X), the amplitude ratios (2X/1X, 3X/1X), and the amplitude at the sidebands of the supply frequency (50Hz ± 2 x slip, 50Hz ± rotation speed). For each sensor signal 30

features were extracted (Table 1), resulting in a total number of 480 features for the 16 signals for each measurement. These time and frequency domain features are standard for condition monitoring of induction motors [7][9].

B. Feature selection and parameter setting

The ReliefF algorithm has three parameters: m , k and τ . Parameter m represents the number of iterations used for training the algorithm. If the training set is relatively small, it is common choice to set m to the number of observations creating an exhaustive search [10]. In the results described here, m was set to the number of observations in the training set. The number of nearest neighbors k is used for calculating the nearest k hits and k nearest misses, controlling the locality of the estimates. If k is too small, the algorithm may not be robust to deal with noise, if k is too big, the algorithm may not be able to capture the local dependencies between the features. In this analysis k was set to 10, which is the default value proposed in the literature [6].

Parameter τ is the feature relevancy threshold, which determines which features are selected based on the feature ranking. If the relevancy of a feature is below τ it is considered unimportant and is not selected. The upper bound for τ was proposed as

$$\tau \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha \cdot m}} \quad (3),$$

where α is the probability of accepting an irrelevant feature as relevant [11]. However the upper bound for τ is very loose and in most of the cases much smaller values should be sufficient. In the analysis described here a value of 0.1 was chosen for τ .

Once the features were extracted, the dataset was randomly split into a training set, containing 70% of the data and a test set, containing 30% of the data. The feature selection was applied to the training set via the previously introduced ReliefF algorithm. For each fault category the feature selection step split the training data into two classes: the observations from one particular fault category and the rest of the fault categories classified as ‘others’. The ReliefF algorithm ranked all of the features in order to achieve the best class separation for that particular fault category. This method was conducted 8 times to obtain the feature ranking for each fault category.

C. Overall classification performance

For the purposes of comparison, the Bayesian binary classifier was tested with and without feature selection. Without feature selection, all of the features in the test set were kept and used as inputs for the classifiers. The overall performance was measured by the percentage of correct classifications in the test set, which was 97.69% in this case. With feature selection the classifiers only utilized the features from the test set, which were selected by ReliefF using the training set. The percentage of correct classifications was 99.42% in this case, which is a 1.73% improvement in performance. It has to be noted that these results were achieved by randomly splitting the observations from each fault category to training set and test set using all loading

conditions. In case of using new data recorded from tests with different environmental or loading conditions, there is no guarantee that the selected features will still be the most relevant. Therefore feature selection does not always result in a performance improvement.

TABLE 1.

Extracted features	
1 RMS	16 Amplitude at 50 Hz-rotation speed
2 Skewness	17 Amplitude at 50 Hz+rotation speed
3 Kurtosis	18 Ratio2X1X
4 Maximum Peak	19 Ratio3X1X
5 Crest factor	20 Envelope at 1X
6 Peak-to-peak	21 Envelope at 2X
7 Spectrum Area	22 Envelope at 3X
8 Frequency Center	23 Envelope at 50 Hz
9 Amplitude at 50 Hz	24 Envelope at 100 Hz
10 Amplitude at 100 Hz	25 Envelope at 50 Hz-2s
11 Amplitude at 1X	26 Envelope at 50 Hz+2s
12 Amplitude at 2X	27 Envelope at 50 Hz-rotation speed
13 Amplitude at 3X	28 Envelope at 50 Hz+rotation speed
14 Amplitude at 50 Hz-2s	29 Envelope of Ratio2X1X
15 Amplitude at 50 Hz+2s	30 Envelope of Ratio3X1X

V. DISCUSSION

A. Selected features by sensor type

Table 2 shows the 60 most relevant features by fault category. The table is color coded according to sensor type, see the corresponding color legends. If considering the top 10 relevant features for all fault categories, it may be observed that no features derived from voltage or microphone signals appear. Among the top 60 relevant features, the features derived from microphone and voltage signals appear the least frequently, indicating their limited importance. Features derived from current and vibration are the most dominant, while Microflow signals are of moderate importance. The voltage signal does not appear among the relevant features for F2, F6 and F7, in these cases the voltage signal can be excluded from the diagnostics.

B. Selected features by signal processing method

Table 2 also provides information on which specific feature is extracted from the measured signal, in accordance with the features listed in Table 1. The results emphasize the importance of domain knowledge in induction motor condition monitoring, as many of the features identified as most relevant by the proposed algorithm align with those recommended in existing available literature related to diagnosing rotor, stator and bearing faults.

TABLE 2.

The 60 most relevant features by fault category								Legend	
	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	
1	1	21	10	9	9	22	8	8	Current
2	4	22	8	1	1	10	7	9	Voltage
3	6	4	1	4	4	4	8	11	Vibration
4	7	10	4	6	6	10	1	16	Microflow
5	1	3	6	10	10	6	11	16	Microphone
6	4	10	22	7	8	8	8	11	
7	6	21	4	10	1	10	16	17	
8	7	6	1	8	4	1	11	17	
9	10	29	21	10	6	4	6	12	
10	22	8	10	21	4	6	8	12	
11	8	10	11	8	8	11	8	8	
12	21	8	9	1	5	1	4	12	
13	10	1	1	4	10	21	20	17	
14	2	9	7	6	5	16	7	7	
15	1	1	4	21	11	15	7	9	
16	5	1	6	3	7	20	16	5	
17	7	4	1	27	3	12	8	6	
18	21	6	8	21	7	15	7	17	
19	4	4	7	22	20	14	7	17	
20	6	6	4	11	16	2	7	28	
21	1	4	6	8	21	7	4	9	
22	7	8	16	7	8	12	8	11	
23	11	7	7	8	8	14	8	9	
24	10	17	7	10	1	13	6	17	
25	20	8	8	16	10	15	4	28	
26	4	6	8	22	10	16	3	15	
27	8	1	7	1	22	12	16	16	
28	10	11	7	7	4	14	5	22	
29	16	7	7	10	5	9	8	17	
30	7	10	7	20	6	1	6	18	
31	10	2	6	4	2	7	15	9	
32	7	9	20	21	10	17	21	28	
33	8	1	7	10	5	8	7	12	
34	7	7	21	7	7	7	14	27	
35	20	5	10	7	1	10	26	17	
36	7	7	11	5	4	4	4	10	
37	9	16	27	1	6	6	6	20	
38	8	22	10	4	7	7	19	1	
39	1	7	2	6	7	1	5	8	
40	20	20	22	7	7	7	25	18	
41	6	1	22	7	11	4	28	4	
42	7	21	16	11	7	6	10	6	
43	11	7	7	5	7	5	13	3	
44	21	9	5	7	10	13	5	13	
45	10	7	10	7	7	16	10	28	
46	4	7	10	7	7	7	1	10	
47	3	7	27	10	5	7	19	10	
48	16	10	4	2	17	7	18	2	
49	6	27	3	21	21	7	9	9	
50	7	11	8	20	8	8	1	1	
51	22	10	4	3	8	8	4	5	
52	7	1	21	8	16	7	4	14	
53	27	9	9	3	9	11	6	7	
54	22	7	8	9	6	17	16	9	
55	3	5	4	16	22	8	11	3	
56	27	18	7	6	8	13	5	17	
57	16	8	16	22	8	7	6	13	
58	9	9	16	16	8	17	1	8	
59	4	8	11	3	16	11	23	11	
60	27	4	6	11	21	7	7	1	

The most widely used approach for bearing fault diagnosis found in existing literature is the frequency domain analysis of measured vibrations, as the defects in rolling element bearings create short impulses, which can be detected in the frequency domain [12][13]. It may be observed in Table 2 that in the case of bearing fault detection (F7), frequency domain features extracted from the vibration signals are identified as the most relevant. This aligns with existing domain knowledge.

The frequency analysis of currents, or motor current signature analysis, is a proven method for diagnosing electrical and magnetic field faults in induction motors [14] [15]. In the case of stator faults (F2, F3, F4, and F5) and rotor fault (F6), it may be observed in Table 2 that features based on frequency domain analysis of measured currents are the most relevant among the top 30 features.

The proposed method also highlights those features which hold less information about particular faults. For example, features based on Envelope at 50 Hz, Envelope at 50 Hz-2s, Envelope at 50 Hz+2s and Envelope of Ratio2X1X appear only once, while Envelope at 100 Hz, Envelope at 150 Hz and Envelope of Ratio3X1X do not appear at all. For the faults investigated in this paper, features based on these metrics do not hold any significant value; for other types of fault not considered in this investigation, these indicators may have more value.

Although the microphone and Microflown acoustic signals are prone to background noise, their Spectrum Area feature appears for most of the fault categories as a relevant indicator. The Microflown signals also provide the top 8 relevant features for the healthy motor.

Whilst it may be observed that time domain and frequency domain features are relevant for all fault categories, in general, frequency domain features appear to be slightly more dominant. This is likely due to the fact that features based on frequency domain analysis are typically more discriminatory than time domain features. Frequency analysis is used to extract components at specific frequencies associated with the dynamic signatures excited by a fault. By targeting specific frequencies of interest, the analysis is better able to discriminate between different fault modes and noise. This further illustrates the value of domain knowledge in selecting and constructing features; in this instance, applying domain expertise in the proper selection of particular frequencies of interest to be analyzed in the frequency domain. More advanced signal processing approaches, better suited for extracting specific aspects of fault signatures, may yield features with even greater relevance to monitoring specific fault modes. The finding that as a first consideration, domain knowledge should be applied in a feature selection problem in order to create the most informative features possible, agrees with classical literature in the field of feature selection [16].

It should also be noted that the analysis was performed on experimental data recorded both for different loading conditions and for different levels of environmental noise. The results therefore relate to features which are best suited for diagnosing particular faults, regardless of loading or noise conditions. In the future, the influence of loading and noise on

the relevancy of a particular feature may also be evaluated by comparing the results obtained for each different loading and noise condition.

C. Similarity of selected features for fault type

Another way to interpret and utilize the results of feature selection is to consider how many features provided the most relevant information for multiple fault categories. Table 3 below gives a comparison of how many features appeared in the top 60 relevant features for any two fault categories.

TABLE 3.

The similarity of the top 60 relevant features by fault category								
	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
F0		46	50	48	46	38	26	22
F1	46		48	48	47	37	26	24
F2	50	48		50	48	38	33	26
F3	48	48	50		50	37	26	26
F4	46	47	48	50		37	28	25
F5	38	37	38	37	37		24	16
F6	26	26	33	26	28	24		13
F7	22	24	26	26	25	16	13	

Fault F0-F4, which include data recorded from the healthy motor and from four severities of stator fault have 46-50 shared features out of the top 60 relevant features. This results may be somewhat expected given the similarity of these fault types. F6 (rotor fault: two broken rotor bars) and F7 (bearing fault: outer raceway defect) are the most different faults. This is reflected in Table 3 as these two fault modes share only 13 common features among the top 60 relevant features for their respective fault categories.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has investigated new applications of the ReliefF feature selection approach for the condition monitoring of induction motors. The multi-class classification problem with several fault categories was decomposed to two-class classification problems in order to use the best subset of features for diagnosing different bearing, stator and rotor faults. The method proved to be suitable for identifying which signal processing techniques and sensors are the most relevant for monitoring a certain fault class. The similarities between relevant features for fault categories can help in identifying similar faults. By considering multiple loading and noise conditions, the obtained results indicate features which are best suited for diagnosing specific faults, regardless of loading or noise conditions; information which can help in designing more robust monitoring systems. The results obtained also reinforce the importance of domain knowledge in selection of appropriate sensors and signal processing approaches which

are able to discriminate both different faults from one another and from ambient noise.

The limitation of the described method for condition monitoring applications is that in the case of using data with different environmental or loading conditions than used in the training set, there is no guarantee that the selected features are still the most relevant or that the relevancy thresholds still hold. Therefore it is advised to use it as a preliminary feature evaluation method in order to have a better understanding for the features and the faults.

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